

Trends in Spatial Distribution and Characteristics of HIV Clusters in Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Introduction: Nigeria bears the highest burden of HIV in Sub-Saharan Africa with about 1.9 million of the population infected with the virus. **Objectives:** This study aimed to describe the spatial distribution and characteristics of HIV clusters in Cross River State, Nigeria. **Methods:** The study used a retrospective cohort design to track activities of Community ART Management (CAM) teams over a period of eight months (January-August, 2020). The essence was to determine their contribution to HIV counselling and testing (HTS) including index case testing (ICT) in relation to the GIS mapped hotspots in the study area. Areas of high positivity using spatial autocorrelation analysis techniques in the data were defined. **Results:** Of the 830 hotspots mapped, the Local Government Areas with the largest number of hotspots included Odukpani, 98(12%), Akamkpa, 89(11%) and Akpabuyo, 82(10%). From January-August, 3170 people tested positive to HIV. HIV-positive yield by geospatial clustering outside of the previously mapped hotspots was 2,339. The distribution by Local Government Area (LGA), showed four LGAs with the largest HIV positive clusters; Yakurr with 495(21%), Akamkpa, 436(19%), Akpabuyo, 409(17%), and Bakassi, 336(14%). Geospatial clustering of HIV positives at the 90% confidence by LGA was 353; at the 95% confidence was 588 and at the 99% confidence was 1,398. The largest clusters at 99% CI were Yakurr, 420(30%), Bakassi, 201(14.4%), Akamkpa, 194(14%), and Akpabuyo, 171(12%). **Conclusion/Recommendations:** HTS and ICT should focus more on these large clusters to maximize efficiency in testing and initiation to HIV care within the state. **Keywords:** GIS, spatial analysis, HIV/AIDS, clusters

Introduction:

For the past decade, achieving the UNAIDS 90:90:90 targets by the year 2020 had been a constant struggle for most countries especially in Sub-Saharan Africa. The first 90, of ensuring that 90% of a population get tested and know their HIV status was an important gateway for achieving the second and third 90s respectively (UNAIDS, 2019). With the commencement of the expanded strategy to end HIV/AIDS using the 95:95:95 targets, it is expected that 95% of all people living with HIV know their status; 95% of all people diagnosed with HIV receive sustained antiretroviral therapy (ART); and 95% of all people on ART are virally suppressed. However, difficulties still arise in communities where socio-cultural practices that increase peoples' risk of getting infected with HIV, coupled with HIV-related stigma are still very prevalent (UNAIDS, 2016, 2019).

One of the prevalent socio-culturally linked risk factors for getting infected by HIV through sexual intercourse is multiple sexual partners. Having multiple sexual partners is a norm in Nigeria rather than the exception. In the 2018 Health and Demographic Survey, of the 864 men surveyed who said they have had two or more sexual partners in the past 12 months, 84.5% were in a polygamous relationship. Those within this same group who have had sexual intercourse with someone who was not their wife, 4.7% were in a polygamous marriage (NDHS, 2018). Similarly in a sample of 5,082 young men, over a quarter of them said they had engaged in sexual intercourse outside of their regular relationships (NDHS, 2018). This multiple sexual partner index is not peculiar to men alone. However, majority of women who had multiple sexual partners were those who were single, divorced or widowed (NDHS, 2018). From a sample of 15, 284 young women between the ages of 15-24, 1.3% have had sex with two or more partners while 12.6% have had sex with someone who was not their husband within the past year.

According to the Nigeria AIDS Indicator Survey (NAIIS), about 1.9 million Nigerians are infected with HIV. Nigeria therefore bears the highest burden of the condition in Sub-Saharan Africa just by virtue of its population alone. Unfortunately, this places Nigeria as a country with the largest population of babies born with HIV (Cohen, 2018). Cross River State has a 2% HIV prevalence which is higher than the national prevalence of 1.4. Even though the state has one of the lowest prevalence in the country, Cross River still has an unmet need of 18,844 and an estimated 37493 people living with HIV (PLWHIV). When these numbers are juxtaposed on the state estimated population of 4.2 million spread over 20,146 k² on difficult terrains and seasonal inaccessibility to some parts of the state, it provokes the need to develop and deploy innovative methods in order to achieve the first 95 of the current UNAIDS 95-95-95 targets (UNAIDS, 2019).

Objectives: The main objective of this study was to compare trends in spatial distribution and characteristics of HIV clusters in Cross River State, Nigeria from January to August 2020.

Methods

This study used a retrospective cohort design to track activities of CAM teams over a period of eight months (January-August, 2020) to determine their contribution to HIV counselling and testing in relation to the geographically mapped hotspots in the study area. This study involved all healthcare facilities in Cross River State supported by the Strengthening Integrated Delivery of HIV/AIDS Service Delivery (SIDHAS) project. These 49 sites, a combination of public and private health facilities, are primarily found in the Central and Southern Senatorial Districts of Cross River State, Nigeria. While facility-based HIV counseling and testing are encouraged, new strategies for HIV case identification were initiated as part of the Differentiated Service Delivery (DSD) approach to complement facility efforts. These included but were not limited to Index Case Testing (ICT), use of Geographic Information Systems (GIS)(Ord & Getis, 2010) for identifying and mapping of HIV hotspots, providing integrated services and formation and mobilization of the Community ART Management (CAM) Teams to help take HIV care into the community, particularly hard-to-reach areas. The operations of these strategies were not mutually exclusive. Sixteen Community ART Management (CAM) Teams were formed to augment existing facility-based care. The CAM teams are multidisciplinary mini mobile clinics that serve the communities in the 13 Local Government Areas where the SIDHAS-supported sites are located (Egbe et al., 2020). All CAM team members and the facility-based healthcare teams attend the daily situation room meetings to report their activities and also participate in monthly capacity building sessions to stay updated on best practices in HIV care.

CAM teams were trained on community mapping techniques using a combination of the Open Data Kit (ODK) and the GIS software for both collection and processing of field data. They begin testing and mapping from pre-targeted hotspots which included Traditional Birth Attendants (TBA), Patent Medicine Vendors, Prayer Houses (PH) and Fishermen Jetties. These places are believed from past community outreach experience to have the potential of yielding higher proportion HIV positive cases from the cache of those tested. This study adopted a 75-meter radius distance from the mapped locations of the pre-targeted hot spot as the “Radius of Influence” (ROI) (Egbe et al., 2020). All those offered HTS within this ROI were assumed to be associated or gotten from that pre-targeted hot spot. Conversely, all persons tested for HIV outside the ROI were assumed not to be associated with the pre-targeted hot spots. For any client who tests positive, the coordinates of the location are recorded in the ODK and the relative distance to the pre-targeted hotspots are determined. This will enable the description and/or characterization of the clusters based on HIV burden. Equally, the team follows up with the identified clients to elicit all sexual partners who in turn get HIV counseling and testing. These clients (HIV-positive) are then enrolled into care using differentiated service delivery (DSD); initiation of ART, linkage to a health facility, enrollment into Community ART Clubs (CARC), or Community Pharmacy ARV Refill Program (CPARP) depending on the needs and preferences of the client.

After using the ODK to capture the locations where HIV positive clients were identified, the data is transmitted electronically and plotted to determine the relative yields for different locations. The data was analyzed using the Geographic Information System (GIS) software. Based on data distribution, the researchers described areas

of high positivity using spatial autocorrelation analysis techniques to identify locations of statistically significant ‘hotspots’ in the data. This research defined three categories of clusters as follows;

- Hotspot at 99% confidence with z-score ≥ 2.58 ; p-value ≤ 0.01
- Hotspot at 95% confidence with z-score ≥ 1.96 and z-score < 2.58 ; $p < 0.05$ and $p > 0.01$
- Hotspot at 90% confidence with z-score ≥ 1.65 and z-score ≤ 1.96 ; $p < 0.1$ and $p > 0.05$ (Egbe et al., 2020; Ord & Getis, 2010)

Results

The CAM teams mapped 830 hotspots in the study. Of these, the Local Government Areas with the largest number of hotspots include Odukpani, 98(12%), Akamkpa, 89(11%) and Akpabuyo, 82(10%) (Figure 1). A total of 3170 people tested positive from January-August, 2020. Of these, 890(28%) were associated with pre-targeted hotspots. Of the seven types of pre-targeted hotspots, health facilities (HF) recorded the highest number of HIV positive cases at 399(45%). This is followed closely by patent medicine vendors (PMV) with 128(14%) (Figure 2). GIS-mapped community HIV testing (HTS) data revealed 195 new hot spots generated in March 2020 & 2348 in August 2020. The result shows that only 10% (171/1719) of new HIV positives identified from March to August, 2020 were in previously predicted hot spots.

Figure 1: Number of Hotspots mapped by Local Government Area

Figure 2: HIV-positive yield from pre-targeted hotspots

HIV positive yield by geospatial clustering outside of the previously mapped hotspots was 2,339. The distribution by Local Government Area (LGA), showed four LGAs with the largest HIV positive clusters to be Yakurr with 495(21%), Akamkpa, 436(19%), Akpabuyo, 409(17%), and Bakassi, 336(14%). Geospatial clustering of HIV positives at the 90% confidence by LGA gave a total of 353. At this confidence level, Akpabuyo cluster was the highest with 97(27%) followed closely by her neighboring LGA, Akamkpa with 67(19%), Yakurr, 45(13%) and Odukpani, 42(12%). The total HIV positives at the 95% confidence was 588. Of these, the largest clusters were Akamkpa, 175(30%), Akpabuyo, 141(24%) and Bakassi, 104(18%). The HIV positives at the 99% confidence were 1,398. The largest clusters were Yakurr, 420(30%), Bakassi, 201(14.4%), Akamkpa, 194(14%), and Akpabuyo, 171(12%) (Figure 3). The recurrence of Akamkpa and Akpabuyo LGAs in all the three categories is suggestive of a higher HIV burden in these places.

Figure 3: GIS-informed hotspots at the 90%, 95% and 99% confidence

Discussion:

The study sought to describe the spatial distribution and characteristics of HIV clusters in Cross River State. This spatially distributed clusters define trends that are guided by uniformity in HIV positivity yield. The study shows that the number of newly generated/statistically inferred hot spots rose from 195 in March 2020 to 2339 in August 2020. It was also noticed that, unlike the first set of hot spots (generated in March) where the number of hot spots within the 90% CI occurred the most and those in the 99% CI occurred the least, the reverse seems to be the case following the recent analysis in August, 2020 (Egbe et al., 2020). The trend reveals that the hot spots in the 99% CI "perhaps the best set of clusters to focus on" are more - 90% CI [353], 95% CI [588], 99% [1,398] spread across respective LGAs. It is important to point out that geospatial clustering of community HTS data helps in identifying new locations of Hot spots in communities – teams are guided to locations with inferences suggesting high positivity rates. While the conventional HTS gives a peripheral information on disease clusters, GIS is meant to be a complementary tool (Tanser & Le Sueur, 2002) to support HIV case finding modalities such as Index Case Testing (ICT) (FHI360, 2020) with specific detailed description of the geolocation where clients were identified. Additionally, GIS is effective in identifying areas with high disease burden to help the healthcare professionals channel resources appropriately (Tsai, Lin, Chu, & Perng, 2009).

With the increase in the volume of data (spatial proximity and spread of our mapped HTS points), this suggests we may be closing in on more of the locations (hitherto hidden) with the 95% and 99% CI which gives us further leverage in better targeting case finding. Geospatial clustering of community HTS data helps in identifying new locations of Hot spots in communities – teams are guided to locations with inferences suggesting high positivity rates. Following increased volume of data, we have seen a few other LGAs such as Yakurr, Odukpani, Ikom, and Boki showing a high density of clusters within the 90%, 95% and 99% CI, in addition to the previously known Akamkpa, Bakassi and Akpabuyo LGAs. A similar study in the United States showed that the use of GIS helps in effectively gaining access to communities with high disease burden (Goswami et al., 2012). Another study in Sub-Saharan Africa used GIS to predict acceptability of HIV self-test kits. The distribution trend shows that more rural LGAs seem to yield more HIV positive results even at the 90% CI than LGAs in urban areas. These communities tend to be described as hard-to-reach, have little or no access to healthcare and the residents are more likely to be of lower socio-economic status. Also, residents in these areas have co-morbidities such sexually transmitted Infections (STIs) which are hardly given sufficient attention in terms of diagnosis and treatment. Studies have shown that geospatial mapping help in uptake of HTS regardless of the location (Hlongwa, Mashamba-Thompson, Makhunga, & Hlongwana, 2019).

Recommendation: Akamkpa, Akpabuyo and Bakassi in the South Senatorial District and Yakurr, Ikom and Boki in Central Senatorial Districts show significant clustering of HIV positive persons. Focusing on these rural and semi-urban areas for mapping and HIV testing including self-tests and Pre-Exposure Prophylaxis (PrEP) is recommended as a means of attaining the UNAIDS targets to achieve epidemic control of HIV

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Conflict of interest:

The authors have no conflicts to report

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